

Retrospective Study on Clinical Profile of Severe Malaria in Children Admitted in a Tertiary Care Centre of Central India

P. Verma, *U. S. Shukla, A. Kalraiya

Department of Pediatrics, *Department of Community Medicine, People's College of Medical Sciences & Research Centre, Bhanpur, Bhopal - 462037

(Received November, 2013)

(Accepted January, 2014)

Abstract:

Severe malaria is a potentially fatal condition encountered in all age groups and if not treated timely can cause mortality. The present retrospective study was conducted over 4 years (2009-2012) to assess clinical and haemato-biochemical profile of all severe malaria cases admitted in pediatric ICU. Out of 179 cases of malaria, 102 (56.9%) children had severe malaria. Maximum number of patients were of plasmodium falciparum 59 (57.8%), Plasmodium vivax was documented in 13.7% and mixed infection in 27.4% cases. The age of the patients with severe malaria ranged from 4 months to 12 years mean age being 6 year. Sixty four (62.7%) of them were boys and rest of them were girls. Frequent manifestations encountered were severe anemia (65.6%), followed by impaired consciousness (20.5%), hemoglobinuria (19.6%), multiple convulsions (17.6%), circulatory collapse (10.7%), clinical icterus with multisystem involvement (11%), respiratory distress (6.8%), prostration (5.8%), spontaneous bleeding (5.8%), metabolic acidosis (3.9%) and renal impairment (1.9%). Mortality occurred only in children with Plasmodium falciparum infestation. Outcome was favourable in 88.2% children who were discharged after clinical improvement; where as 4.9% patients died and 6.86% critically ill patients left against medical advice.

Key Words: Severe Malaria, Falciparum, Mixed, Vivax.

Introduction:

Malaria in its severe form is one of the leading cause of mortality in all ages in tropical countries. Across the world, South East Asian Region bears the second largest burden of malaria (13.0%), being next only to African region (81.0%). Among South-East Asia region, India shares two-third of the burden (61.0%) followed by Indonesia (22.0%) and Myanmar (12.0%)¹. Unlike in Africa, where most of the deaths are reported in infants and children, it is seen that in India, the deaths in infants and children below 14 years of age is only 20.6%. According to an estimate, from 2009-2012, Madhya Pradesh, accounted for 6.0% (72 million) of the total population of India (1.23 billion), but contributed to 6.2% of the total cases of malaria². Plasmodium falciparum (Pf) is the main culprit responsible for severe and complicated malaria³. Recent studies suggest that Plasmodium vivax (Pv) is also equally responsible for severe form of malaria⁴. According to World Health Organization, severe malaria is defined as a patient with Pf asexual parasitemia plus at least one or more of the following

clinical or laboratory features: cerebral malaria, metabolic acidosis, severe anemia, hypoglycemia, hemoglobinuria, circulatory collapse, acute renal failure and acute pulmonary edema etc³. Most of the research work on profile of severe malaria in children are reported from Africa and few from India^{4,5}. But very few published research articles are available from Madhya Pradesh especially from Bhopal district⁶. The aim of the present study, therefore, was to find out clinical and haemato-biochemical profile of severe malaria in children admitted in our setup.

Material & Methods:

The present study was conducted in Peoples College of Medical Sciences & Research centre, a tertiary care teaching hospital of Bhopal in Central India. Being a teaching hospital and tertiary referral centre, case input is primarily from Bhopal district and also from bordering districts (Vidisha and Raisen district).

This was a retrospective, hospital based clinico-epidemiological study. Case records of confirmed malaria patients admitted between January 2009 to December 2012 were retrieved from medical record department and data was collected in a preformed proforma and analyzed by SPSS 20.0 software. Chi square test was used and $p < 0.05$ was

Corresponding Author: Dr. Pramila Verma, Department of Pediatrics, People's College of Medical Sciences & Research Centre, Bhopal 462037
Phone No.: +91 9165595105
E-mail: drpramilav@yahoo.com

considered significant. Out of 179 children of malaria admitted in the department of paediatric, 102 children satisfied the World Health Organization (WHO) criteria of severe malaria guidelines 2010 and admitted in Pedaiatric Intensive Care Unit³. All the criterias of severe malaria were considered except for hyperparasitaemia and hyperlactataemia because these test could not be done in our set up.

Permission from institutional research and ethical committee was taken before commencement of the study.

Results:

In the present study, *P. falciparum* was the main infecting species in both uncomplicated malaria and severe malaria cases (Table I). Maximum number of children got admitted after rainy season and peak admission were from September to November (Fig. I). Year wise distribution of Pf, Pv & mixed infection is shown in Fig. II. Maximum number of patients were of Pf (57.8%); Pv was documented in 13.7% and mixed infection in 27.4% cases.

The age of patients ranged from four months to twelve years with a mean age of 6 years. In the present study, boys (62.7%) outnumbered girls (37.3%). Majority of patients (55.0%) belonged to rural area. Mean duration between appearance of the first symptom and reporting to the department was 8.3 days. Forty percent children had more than one manifestations of severe malaria. Clinical manifestations of these cases remained static over the

study period (Table IIa). Prostration was seen more in Pv group while hemoglobinuria was common in Pf group (Table-IIb).

Fever was the chief presenting complaint in almost all the cases (97.0%) and mean temperature at the time of admission was 99.9° F (range 98.6° F to 104° F). Other presenting complaints of children were: repeated vomiting (41.0%), decreased oral acceptance (22.5%), clinical hemoglobinuria (19.6%), cough (18.6%), abdominal pain (16.6%), impaired consciousness (20.5%) and seizures (17.6%).

Of the 21 children with impaired consciousness, eighteen had multiple convulsions. Lumbar puncture was done in 15 of them and CSF was normal. Eleven children had hypotensive shock requiring ionotropic support. Spontaneous bleeding was seen in six patients out of which one patient died and three patients left against medical advice.

All the patients (n=67; 65.6%) with severe anaemia (haemoglobin <5 g/dl) were given packed red blood cell transfusion. Thrombocytopenia was also seen in all the 3 groups 62.7% (Table III). But platelet transfusion was required in only four children (3 were Pf positive and one was of mixed infection). Bilirubin > 3 mg/dl was seen in 13 patients, whereas, clinical jaundice with multisystem involvement was seen in twelve children. Raised serum transaminases above the normal reference range (SGOT: 30-35 IU/L; SGPT:40-45 IU/L) was seen in (52.9% children, whereas serum transaminases level >150 IU/L was seen in only 10 children. Table III shows that on admission, hyperglycemia was noted in 15 children,

Fig.I: Severe malaria patients admissions during study period.

Fig. II: Type of Plasmodium species in severe malaria patients during study period.

Table I: Distribution of admitted malaria cases during study period.

Plasmodium species	Uncomplicated cases	severe malaria	Total
<i>P.falciparum</i>	37 (48.0%)	59(57.8%)	96 (53.6%)
<i>P.vivax</i>	34 (44.1%)	15(13.7%)	49 (27.3%)
Mixed	6 (7.5%)	28 (27.4%)	34 (18.9%)
Total	77 (43.1%)	102 (56.9%)	179 (100%)

Table II (a): Clinical manifestations of severe malaria over four years.

Who criteria	2009 (n=25)	2010 (n=28)	2011 (n=34)	2012 (n=15)	Total
Impaired consciousness	7(28.0%)	5(17.8%)	6(17.64%)	3(20.0%)	21(20.5%)
Prostration	2(8.0%)	1(3.5%)	2(5.8%)	1(6.6%)	6 (5.8%)
Multiple convulsions	4(16.0%)	6 (21.0%)	7(20.8%)	1(6.6%)	18(17.6%)
Respiratory distress	2(8.0%)	1(3.5%)	3 (8.8%)	1 (6.6%)	7(6.8%)
Circulatory collapse	2(8.0%)	2(7.1%)	5(14.7%)	2(13.3%)	11(10.7%)
Clinical jaundice+MS#	3(12.0%)	3(10.7%)	5(14.7%)	1(6.6%)	12(11.0%)
Spontaneous bleeding	2(8.0%)	1(3.5%)	2(5.8%)	1(6.6%)	6(5.8%)
Normocytic anemia	18(72.0%)	22(78.57%)	17(50.0%)	10(66.6%)	67(65.6%)
Hemoglobinuria	5(20.0%)	4(14.2%)	7(20.5%)	4(26.6%)	20(19.6%)
Renal impairment	0	0	1(2.9%)	1(6.66%)	2(1.9%)
Hypoglycemia	0	0	1(2.9%)	0	1(0.9)
Metabolic acidosis	0	2(7.1%)	1(2.9%)	1(6.66%)	4(3.9%)

Prostration– generalised weakness so that patient cannot walk , , Circulatory collapse – systolic BP < 50 mm hg , # Multisystem involvement i.e. ≥ 2 system involvement, Renal impairment- s.creatinine > 265 μ mol/l, Hypoglycemia- blood glucose < 40 mg/dl , Metabolic acidosis-plasma bicarbonate <15 mmol/l.

Table II (b): Clinical manifestations in Pf, Pv and mixed infection.

Who criteria	<i>P. falciparum</i>	<i>P.vivax</i>	mixed infection	<i>p</i> -value
	(n=59)	(n=15)	(n=28)	
Inpaired consciousness	14(23.0%)	3(20.0%)	4(14.2%)	0.595
Prostration	1(1.6%)	4(26.6%)	1(3.5%)	0.001
Multiple convulsions	11(18.6%)	5(33.0%)	2(7.1%)	0.095
Respiratory distress	5(8.4%)	0	2(7.1%)	0.510
Circulatory collapse	8(13.5%)	0	3(10.7%)	0.319
Clinical jaundice+MS	8 (13.5%)	3(20.0%)	1(3.5%)	0.226
Spontaneous bleeding	3(5.0%)	2(13.3%)	1(3.5%)	0.398
Normocytic anemia	40(67.0%)	7(46.6%)	20 (71.0%)	0.231
Hemoglobinuria	16(27.0%)	0	4 (14.2%)	0.043
Renal impairment	1(1.6%)	1(6.6%)	0	0.315
Hypoglycemia	1(1.6%)	0	0	0.692
Metabolic Acidosis	4(6.7%)	0	0	0.219

three of them required subcutaneous insulin injections. Urinary tract infection was diagnosed in seven patients (pus cells more than 10/mm³ in uncentrifuged urine) with culture positive of *E.coli* in one.

Metabolic acidosis was seen in four patients, all of them were *P.falciparum* positive. Majority of patients with hypoalbuminemia belonged to *P.falciparum* group. All children of study group were

treated with artemisinin combination therapy (ACT) as per WHO guidelines 2010. Outcome was favourable in 88.2% patients who were discharged after clinical recovery; five *P.falciparum* positive patients died, 2 of them were less than two years of age and both died within few hours of admission in the hospital. Seven very sick patients left against medical advice.

Table III: Associated laboratory abnormalities related to severe malaria

Parameter	n=102	Pf (n=59)	Pv(n=15)	Mixed (n=28)	p-value
Thrombocytopenia #	64(62.7%)	39(66.1%)	11(73.3%)	14(50.0%)	0.229
Hypoalbuminemia\$	7(6.8%)	6 (10.1)	0	1(3.5%)	0.09
Hyperglycemia*	15(14.7%)	12 (20.3%)	0	3(10.7%)	0.109
Raised bilirubin	13(12.7%)	6 (10.1%)	2 (13.3%)	5(17.8%)	0.061
Increased hepatic enz^	10(9.0%)	7 (11.8%)	3 (20.0%)	0	0.07

Cut off's taken for this study; # Platelet count <1.0 lakh , \$ serum albumin <2.5 mg/dl; *Random blood sugar >200 mg/dl, raised bilirubin >3 mg/dl, ^Amonotransferase > 150 IU

Discussion:

This retrospective study revealed that among 102 children with severe malaria, 57.8% patients were positive for *P.falciparum*. Similar observation were made by Jain et al from Jabalpur⁶. The result of the present study is in contrast to that of Kaushik et al, who reported 24 *P.vivax* positive patients out of 27 cases of severe malaria⁴.

In the present study, maximum number of cases were observed in the months from September to November. However, Tagle & Cabanban reported a maximum number of malaria patients in the month of April from Manila⁷.

In a study by Yadav et al⁵ cerebral malaria, severe anemia and shock were more frequently observed in *P.falciparum* group, while hepatic, renal, respiratory, and bleeding complications were more commonly seen in *P.vivax* positive patients. In the present study, there was no statistically significant difference in clinical manifestations among all the three groups except for the prostration which was more frequent in *P.vivax* group and hemoglobinuria in *P.falciparum* group.

In 84.0% of patients, fever responded to first dose of Artesunate. This is in accordance with the results reported by Arnaud⁸. Fever was followed by impaired consciousness in 21 patients, 4 of them had unarousable coma and 2 died within few hours of admission.

In the present study, 67(65.6%) patients had severe anaemia out of which 2 died and 4 critically ill patients left against medical advice. Arnaud et al⁸ also reported that severe anaemia (67.8%,) was the commonest feature of severe malaria. The pathophysiology of anaemia in malaria is multifactorial. It results from accelerated red cell destruction and removal by the spleen in conjunction with ineffective erythropoiesis.

Thrombocytopenia is considered to be caused by increased splenic sequestration, immune mediated destruction and shortened platelet survival. In the

present study, thrombocytopenia was seen in 62.7% patients. Though thrombocytopenia was more (73.0%) common in vivax group but profound fall (<20,000 platelet count) was seen in *P.falciparum* group, 3 of them required platelet transfusion. The result is similar to that reported by Shelthy et al from Karnataka⁹. Leukocytosis was seen in 14.7% and leucopenia in 7.8% patients in the present study. Both leukocytosis and leucopenia are known in malaria although there is paucity of literature in pediatric age group^{10,11}.

High coloured urine (clinical hemoglobinuria) was present in 20 patients on admission which got cleared in few days. Routine microscopy of urine did not show RBCs in any of the patient. Only one patient was found to be G-6PD deficient in our study. The results are consistent with those of Wasiu et al¹².

Jaundice in malaria results from hemolysis of both parasitized and non-parasitized red cells as well as malarial hepatitis. Raised liver enzymes occurs because of injury to hepatocyte and cholestasis. In the present study, a total bilirubin of more than 3 mg/dl was seen in 12.7% children whereas, clinical jaundice with multisystem involvement was seen in 11.0% children. Hepatitis was present in 9.0% of children as indicated by elevated levels of enzymes although other causes of hepatitis were not ruled out. There is scarcity of published literature on malarial hepatopathy in children. In acute malaria, hepatic dysfunction is reversible and patients respond favourably to antimalarial therapy with no residual effects¹³.

The sequestration of erythrocytes, containing metabolically active parasite in the vascular bed of internal organs can elucidate almost all the pathological events in severe and complicated *P.falciparum* malaria. Malarial parasites also induces the release of cytokines like TNF-alpha, IL-1 and IL-6 that initiate many of the pathological process causing manifestations of malaria.

Atypical presentation encountered in the present study was hyperglycemia which was found in 14.0% children; it could be explained as stress induced

hyperglycemia. Stress induced hyperglycemia commonly occurs during critical illness in children, even in those with previously normal glucose homeostasis¹⁴. Hyperglycemia in severe malaria was also reported by Dass et al¹⁵. Acute Disseminated Encephalomyelitis (ADEM) was seen in one patient who was P.vvax positive and diagnosed by MRI; it was also reported by Goyal et al¹⁶.

A total of 5 patients died; all of them were P.falciparum positive and had more than one manifestations of severe malaria. It was also reported by Tripathy et al¹⁷. Three of them died within the first 24 hours of hospitalization. This is in accordance with the result reported by from Kenya by Obonyo et al¹⁸.

Since this was a retrospective study with small sample size, we could not demonstrate any cyclical changes in clinical profile of severe malaria over a period of four years. There is a need of prospective study with bigger sample size to find out any changing trend over years.

References:

1. World Health Organization: World malaria report. WHO Geneva; 2012.
2. Malaria situation in India (2009-2013). In: National Vector Borne Disease Control Programme. Ministry of Health & Family Welfare, Delhi.
3. World Health Organization: The guidelines for the treatment of malaria. 2nd Edn.; WHO Geneva; 2010
4. Kaushik JS, Gomber S, Dewan P: Clinical and epidemiological profile of severe malaria in children from Delhi, India. *J Health Popul Nutri* 2012, 30(1):113-116.
5. Yadav D, Chandra J, Aneja S, Kumar V, Kumar P, Dutta AK: Changing Profile of Severe Malaria in North Indian Children. *Indian J Pediatr*, 2012;79(4):483-487.
6. Jain V, Nagpal AC, Joel PK, Shukla M, Singh MP, Gupta RB, Dash AP, Mishra Sk, Udhayakumar V, Stiles JK, Singh N: Burden of cerebral malaria in Central India (2004-2007). *Am J Trop Med Hyg*, 2008;79(4):636-642.
7. Tagle RS, Cabanban AB: Severe and complicated malaria at San Lazaro Hospital. *Phil J Microbiol Infect Dis*, 1992; 22(1):4-10.
8. Dzeing-Ella A, Nze Obiang PC, Tchoua R, Planche T, Mboza B, Mbounja M, Muller-Roemer U, Jarvis J, Kendjo E, Ngou-Milama E, Kremsner PG, Krishna S, Kombila M: Severe falciparum malaria in Gabonese children: clinical and laboratory features. *Malar J*, 2005;4:1-8.
9. Shetty G, Avabratha KS, Gonsalves S, Dany A, Rai BS: Thrombocytopenia in children with malaria-A study from coastal Karnataka, *India Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Disease*, 2012;2(2)107-109.
10. Beale PJ, Cormack JD, Oldrey TB: Thrombocytopenia in malaria with immunoglobulin (IgM) changes. *Br Med J*, 1972;1(5796):345-349.
11. Adedapo AD, Falade CO, Kotila RT, Ademowo GO: Age as a risk factor for thrombocytopenia and anaemia in children treated for acute uncomplicated falciparum malaria. *J Vector Borne Dis*, 2007;44(4):266-271.
12. Ajetunmobi WA, Orimadegun AE, Brown BJ, Afolabi NK, Olabiyi FA, Anetor J, Omokhodion S, Osinusi K, Akinbami FO, Shokunbi WA, Sodeinde O, Fernandez-Reyes D: Haemoglobinuria among children with severe malaria attending tertiary care in Ibadan, Nigeria *Malar J*, 2012;11:336-343.
13. Ghoda MK: Falciparum hepatopathy: A reversible and transient involvement of liver in falciparum malaria. *Trop Gastroenterol*, 2002;23(2):70-71.
14. Srinivasan V, Spinella PC, Drott HR, Roth CL, Helfaer MA, Nadkarni V: Association of timing, duration, and intensity of hyperglycemia with intensive care unit mortality in critically ill children. *Pediatr Crit Care Med*, 2004;5(4):329-336.
15. Dass R, Barman H, Duwarah SG, Deka NM, Jain P, Choudhury V: Unusual presentations of malaria in children: an experience from a tertiary care center in North East India. *Indian J Pediatr*; 2010;77(6):655-60.
16. Goyal JP, Shah VB, Parmar S: Acute disseminated encephalomyelitis after treatment of *Plasmodium vivax* malaria. *J Vector Borne Dis*, 2012;49(2):119-121.
17. Tripathy R, Parida S, Das L, Mishra DP, Tripathy D, Das MC, Chen H, Maguire JH, Panigrahi P: Clinical Manifestations and Predictors of Severe Malaria in Indian Children. *Pediatrics*, 2007;120(3):e454-e460.
18. Obonyo KC, Vulule J, Akhwale WS, Grobbee DE: In-Hospital Morbidity and Mortality Due to Severe Malarial Anemia in Western Kenya. *Ame J Trop Medi Hyg*, 2007;77(6 suppl.):23-28.

<p>Source of Support : Nil. Conflict of Interest: None declared.</p>
